

“EFFECTS OF STRUCTURED COMPLEMENTARY FEEDING INSTRUCTIONS ON KNOWLEDGE OF MOTHERS OF INFANT, ANTHROPOMETRY AND MORBIDITY STATUS OF INFANTS”

A Report

Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Award
of

POST DOCTORAL FELLOW

by

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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Certificate

This is to certify that entitled “**Effects of Structured Complementary Feeding Instructions on Knowledge of Mothers of Infant, Anthropometry and Morbidity Status of Infants**” submitted by **DR. KOGILA. P** to SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY for the award of the Post-Doctoral Fellow is a Bonafide record of the research work carried out by her under my supervision and guidance. The content of the Report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

Supervisor/ Professor: **DR.PRAVEEN .B. M**

Place : MUKKA

Date : 17/11/2023

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Dr. Kogila.P

Synopsis

Introduction:

“Complementary feeding to infants is the process of starting when breast milk alone is no longer sufficient to meet the nutritional requirements of an infant’s. It should be initiated at 6 months with safe, age-appropriate feeding of solid, semi-solid and soft foods along with breastfeeding at least for the first year of life”¹⁻⁴. The transition of food pattern will take place with the child’s growth, which triples its birth weight by the end of the one year. According to World Health Organization there are 3 key determinants to reduce the infant malnutrition are adequate & appropriate feeding, health care and maternal education, environmental health.⁵⁻⁷

Literature survey:

Zohra.S.et.al. Conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis study on the impact of education & provision of complementary feeding on growth & morbidity in children less than 2 years of age. They have included 16 studies, of which 9 studies provided only education on complementary feeding and 7 studies provided complementary foods with or without education. Over all, education on complementary feeding alone significantly improved Height for age (HAZ) (SMD: 0.23; 95% CI: 0.09, 0.36), Weight for age (WAZ) (SMD 0.16, 95% CI: 0.05, 0.27), and significantly reduced the rates of stunting (RR 0.71: 95% CI: 0.56, 0.91). Thus, further study should focus on Complementary feeding interventions have a potential to improve the nutritional status of children through mother’s education¹⁸.

Saleem.A.F.et.al. A community-based randomized interventional study regarding maternal education on appropriate complementary feeding on the nutritional status of their infant’s was conducted with cluster sampling technique with 212 mothers of infants 6-24 months at urban settings in Karachi, Pakistan. Intervention group had a higher mean weight of 350 g (p=0.001), length of 0.66 cm (p=0.001), and MUAC of 0.46 cm (p=0.002) reduction of stunting and underweight were 10% (84% Vs 74%; OR 8.36 (5.6-12.42) and 5% (25% Vs 20%; OR 0.75 (0.4-1.79) in the intervention compared to the control group CI-95%.

The study recommended that educational inputs to mothers of infant would provide improvement in the infant nutritional status¹⁹.

Research gap identify:

First 1000 days are crucial period for children. Mothers are the vital primary care taker for fulfilling all the needs of infants which will promote good bonding and keen observation of infant for any abnormalities. Many studies show that even educated mothers had lack of knowledge on complementary feeding. SCFI, helps to enhance the mother's knowledge and develop self-confidence of mothers to initiate complementary feeding on time and potentially improve the nutritional status of infant. In view of this, it is necessary to educate the mothers by SCFI which will help to prevent infant malnutrition, morbidity and mortality.

Objectives of the proposed work with justification:

- 1.To assess the knowledge on complementary feeding among mothers of infant visiting Pediatric department in control and study group based on developed tool.
2. To design and develop an educational intervention on complementary feeding in regional language (Tamil), for the mothers' of infant visiting Pediatric department.
- 3.To assess the pretest and posttest levels of knowledge among mothers' of infant on complementary feeding.
- 4.To find out the correlation between the knowledge of mothers' of infant with anthropometric and morbidity status of infants'.
- 5.To find out the association between the anthropometric and morbidity status with selected demographic variables of infants and mothers' of infants.
- 6.To compare between control and study groups level of knowledge with selected demographic variables of mothers' of infant.

Methodology

Quantitative evaluative approach, pretest posttest control group design will be used. The data collection tool is validated and reliability established. Simple Random sampling technique with the sample of 500 mothers of infant are included. Written consent from each participant before collecting the data and confidentiality of data will be maintained. The collected data will be tabulated and analyzed by descriptive and inferential statistics.

Expected outcome of the proposed study:

Primary Outcome: Structured complementary feeding instructions (SCFI) will help the mothers of infant to obtain the knowledge on complementary feeding and promotes the anthropometry and declines the morbidity status of infants.

Secondary Outcome: After the intervention and reinforcement(2) all the mothers of infant will be able to: understand the importance of Complementary feeding along with Breast feeding, understand the signs of readiness of complementary feeding, initiate the complementary feeding on time with appropriate frequency and consistency, realize the need of responsive feeding, practice Hygienic measures during preparation and feeding, improve the self-confidence for feeding during and after illness, reduce the hospital visits and hospitalization, reduce the financial burden of family and society, reduce the stress and discomfort of the family, promote healthy growth and development of infant, decline the infant morbidity and mortality.

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Chapter-1

Introduction

“Complementary feeding to infants is the process of starting when breast milk alone is no longer sufficient to meet the nutritional requirements of an infant’s. It should be initiated at 6 months with safe, age-appropriate feeding of solid, semi-solid and soft foods along with breastfeeding at least for the first year of life”¹⁻⁴.

The transition of food pattern will take place with the child’s growth, which triples its birth weight by the end of the one year. According to World Health Organization there are 3 key determinants to reduce the infant malnutrition are adequate & appropriate feeding, health care and maternal education, environmental health.⁵⁻⁷

Background of the study

The UN estimates that 2.1 million Indian children die before reaching the age of 5 year. Four children die every minute due to preventable illnesses such as diarrhea, typhoid, malaria, measles and pneumonia. Every day 1,000 Indian children die because of diarrhea alone²⁻⁴.

According to UNICEF worldwide statistics (2018), only two fifths of infants of 0-6 month’s age are breastfed exclusively. Only around two thirds are introduced to solid foods in a timely manner^{1,5}. Global Infant mortality rate is 13 deaths / 1000 live births^{2,6}.

Need for the study

First 1000 days are crucial period for child. Mothers are the vital primary care taker for fulfilling all the needs of infants which will promote good bonding and keen observation of an infant for any abnormalities⁸⁻¹⁰ and many studies showed that even educated mother’s lack knowledge on complementary feeding¹¹⁻¹⁴. Structured Complementary Feeding Instructions (SCFI) helps to enhance the mother’s knowledge and develop the self-confidence of mothers to initiate complementary feeding on time and potentially improves the nutritional status of an infant. In view of this, it is necessary to educate the mothers on SCFI to prevent infant malnutrition, morbidity and mortality¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

Chapter-2

Aims and objectives

Aim

The main aim of the study is to develop structured complementary feeding instructions for the mothers of infant (6-12 months) and to evaluate the mother's knowledge on complementary feeding and its efficacy by measuring changes in anthropometric, morbidity status of an infant.

Specific objectives

- 1.To assess the knowledge on complementary feeding among mothers of infant visiting Pediatric department in control and study group based on developed tool.
2. To design and develop an educational intervention on complementary feeding in regional language (Tamil), for the mothers' of infant visiting Pediatric department.
- 3.To assess the pretest and posttest levels of knowledge among mothers' of infant on complementary feeding.
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CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Modified Imogene King's goal attainment model (1981)²⁰⁻²² deals on general system theory, the behavioral sciences, deductive and inductive reasoning. Based on her assumption humans are open systems in constant interaction with their environment. This model has three interacting systems such as personal, interpersonal and social.

Chapter-3

Review of literature

Zohra.S.et.al. (2018) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis on the impact of education & provision of complementary feeding on growth & morbidity in children less than 2 years of age. They have included 16 studies, of which 9 studies provided only education on complementary feeding and 7 studies provided complementary foods with or without education. Over all, education on complementary feeding alone significantly improved Height for age (HAZ) (SMD: 0.23; 95% CI: 0.09, 0.36), Weight for age (WAZ) (SMD 0.16, 95% CI: 0.05, 0.27), and significantly reduced the rates of stunting (RR 0.71: 95% CI: 0.56, 0.91). Thus, further study should focus on Complementary feeding interventions have a potential to improve the nutritional status of children through mother's education ¹⁸.

Saleem.A.F.et.al. (2017) A community-based randomized interventional study regarding maternal education on appropriate complementary feeding on the nutritional status of their infant's was conducted among 212 mothers of infants with age group of 6-24 months by cluster sampling technique at peri urban settings in Karachi, Pakistan. Intervention group had a higher mean weight of 350 g (p=0.001), length of 0.66 cm (p=0.001), and MUAC of 0.46 cm (p=0.002) reduction of stunting and underweight were 10% (84% Vs 74%; OR 8.36 (5.6-12.42) and 5% (25% Vs 20%; OR 0.75 (0.4-1.79) compared to the control group at CI-95%.

The study recommended that educational inputs to mothers of infant would provide improvement in the infant nutritional status ¹⁹.

Highlights of present work

This was an experimental study to assess the effect of SCFI on mother's knowledge, anthropometry and morbidity status of infant's. The experiment designed to establish the cause and effect relationship between associated factors and mothers knowledge on complementary feeding by simple random sampling technique to decrease confounding effect among the groups. The study focused on mother's to extract more accurate effect on maternal knowledge on CF, improvement in infant anthropometry and reduction in morbidity. The large number of sample (n=250) were recruited in each group.

Method of teaching as per Edgar Dale's participatory method using a laptop-assisted talk will give 70% of learning by listening and influenced by it. Novel approach validated self-structured complementary feeding tool were developed based on standardized materials of WHO/UNICEF 2016 manual³ and the local needs. SCFI was very simple and in local language, easily understandable by all mothers' irrespective of age, education and socio-economical category. First education given at 3 months and well-spaced follow-ups with reinforcement at 6 months and 9 months.

Novel approach of self-structured, validated Tool on demographic variables of mother, infant, feeding pattern, knowledge questionnaires on CF, Anthropometry and morbidity scale were considered as strength for this study. Educational sessions were face-to-face with 1:5 ratios. It's very small in number to focus equal attention to all 5 mothers while teaching and clarifying their doubts to enhance the knowledge and confidence. The maternal education sessions were interactive, which eventually produced a positive impact on linear growth of infants in the Group I. Mothers who received the educational intervention had heavier, taller and healthier infants at the end of the intervention than the control group infants.

Chapter-4

Material and methods

Research approach & design

A quantitative evaluative research approach, Randomized pretest and posttest control group fact-finding design was adopted for this study.

Setting of the study

Selected Research Institute, Kelambakkam, Kancheepuram district is the solitary center where the study was conducted in pediatric outpatient departments.

Population

The target population was mothers of infants 3 months to 1 year visited pediatric outpatient department at selected tertiary care hospital.

Sample

All the mothers of infants 3 to 12 months who visited the selected tertiary care hospital in a stipulated time schedule and who fulfills the inclusion criteria and willing to participate in the study.

Sample size

Based on Power analysis $= 2(z\alpha/2 + z\beta)^2 p(1-p)/(p1-p2)$, Estimated sample size was around 234 in each group, considering attrition factor the investigator had increased 5% participants to make it as 250 in each group. $n = 250$

Design effect was taken as 2

Final sample size = $250 \times 2 = 500$

Confidence interval = 95%, Power = 80 %, SE=5%

SCHEMATIC DIAGRAM OF THE STUDY

Figure No: 1. Schematic representation of the study

Sampling criteria

Inclusion criteria

The study includes the infants, who,

- ❖ aged 3 months, who were either exclusively on breast feed or partially breast feed but not initiated complementary feeding.
- ❖ term /appropriate to gestational age.
- ❖ age group between 3months to 1year.
- ❖ attending pediatric outpatient department.

The study includes mothers of infants who,

- ❖ can read, understand Tamil and English.

Exclusion criteria

The study excludes infant's who were,

- ❖ critically ill.
- ❖ diagnosed with mal absorption syndrome.
- ❖ known genetic anomaly, neurological disorder.

The study excludes mothers of infants who,

- ❖ received adequate pretest score ($\geq 76\%$)
- ❖ fails to give consent for any reason.
- ❖ sick.

Sampling technique

Mothers of infant and Infants who fulfilled the inclusion criteria, during the period of study time were considered as Participant. After the screening procedure Simple Random sampling technique was used to assign the recruited participants into Group I and Group II.

Educational intervention on structured complementary feeding instruction

Educational intervention is interactive teaching learning session. The laptop assisted teaching was done by lecture cum discussion with power point show to add interest and aid memory. Laptop assisted teaching was done by the Researcher in the seminar hall in a group of 5 participants (1:5) for 45minutes. The contents covered in the Educational intervention are Breast feeding, Complementary feeding, timely initiation, early initiation and late initiation, responsive feeding, preparation and safe storage, amount & density, meal frequency of complementary

feeding, food consistency, nutrient content of complementary food, feeding after illness, mothers nutrition during feeding, etc.

Development and description of the tool

The following tools were prepared through extensive review of literature on various aspects of complementary feeding, as well as expert's opinion and suggestion also received.

Section-A

Part - I - Demographic variables of mothers of infant.

Part - II- Demographic variables of infant's.

Part- III- Feeding pattern of infant's.

Section-B

Part-I-Structured Questionnaires for assessing the Knowledge of mother's of Infant on Complementary Feeding.

Part-II-Scale for assessing anthropometric outcome of infant's.

Part-III-Scale for assessing morbidity status of infant's.

Part - I -socio-demographic data of mothers of infant

The first part of the tool consists of 15 items in that 13 items were related to socio-demographic data of mother's of infant and 2 were regards to father's. There was no score allotted for demographic questionnaires and the data were used for descriptive statistical analysis to identify the frequency and percentage.

Part - II -socio-demographic data of infants

This tool consists of socio demographic data related to infant's such as gender, birth weight, and date of birth, order of birth and status of immunization. There was no score allotted for demographic questionnaires, the data were used for descriptive statistical analysis to identify the frequency and percentage.

Part - III -feeding pattern of infants

A survey was conducted by using diet recall method to know the type of food and time of initiation. Type of food deals with the feeding pattern of infant's that consists of 20 items.

Section B part-I- questionnaires for assessing the knowledge of mothers of infant on complementary feeding

Self-administered structured questionnaires on complementary feeding were consists of 30 multiple choice questions with four options and it includes various aspects of Breast feeding and Complementary feeding. Each question had one appropriate answer and correct answer was awarded a score of '1', wrong answer was awarded a score of '0'. Maximum knowledge score was 30 and minimum knowledge score was 0. Correct responses of knowledge of mothers of infant were classified into adequate ($\geq 76\%$) moderate (51-75%) and inadequate ($\leq 50\%$).

Part-II- scale for assessing the anthropometric status of infant (Based on world health organization 'z' score interpretation)

It consists of 5 items as follows: Age, Anthropometric indicators for the age like weight, length, chest circumference and mid upper arm circumference of infants. They were assessed towards infant growth with help of Weighing machine, Infantometer and Inch tape. The total score of anthropometric status of infant were graded & interpreted by using WHO guidelines as follows: over nourished ($> +2$ SD from median values), normally nourished (-2 to +2 SD from median values), under nourished (-2 to -3 SD from median values) and severely under nourished (< -3 SD from median values).

Part-III-structured scale for assessing morbidity status of infants

Self-administered rating scale for assessing Morbidity status of infant was developed by the investigator and it consists of 10 questions. Each question had one respective answer based on their infant illness with the score of "1, 2, 3, 4, 5" respectively. The Maximum score of the five point rating scale was "50". The total score of morbidity status of infant were converted in to percentage & interpreted as mild ($\leq 49\%$) moderate (50-75%) and severe ($\geq 76\%$).

Validity and reliability of the tool

Content validity, Construct validity and Criterion Validity were done and incorporated the suggestion given by the experts. Test-retest method, Split - half reliability, Internal consistency- Cronbach's alpha values were as follows $r = 0.821$, $r = 0.772$, $r = 0.798$.

Consideration of ethics

The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board, Institutional Human Ethical Committee (273/IHEC/8-17). Registered in Clinical Trial Registry India (CTRI Registration Number CTRI/2018/01/011275) before enrolling the participants in to the study. The investigator obtained oral and written permission from the respective authorities of the selected study area. Both verbal and written informed consent was obtained from each participant by explaining the purpose of the study prior to the data collection. Assured each participant that the collected data would be used only for the study purpose. All the study participants were informed about the participation in the research, objectives and time involvement of the study. Care taken not to cause discomfort to the study participants. All the participants had the rights to withdraw from the study at any point of the time. No interference to the routine care of the participants while collecting data. Assurance was given to the each participant that the anonymity, confidentiality and participant privacy were guarded throughout and while reporting the study.

Pilot study

Pilot study was conducted with 25 Participant in each group. The analysis was done by using descriptive and inferential statistics. Modifications done after the Pilot study were as follows: duration of educational intervention was extended from 30 minutes to 45 minutes, and head circumference was removed from the anthropometry as suggested by experts. The pilot study participants were not included in main the study.

Chapter-5

Results and data analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to arrange the data in scientific way such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and Inferential statistics was used to test the hypothesis, correlation, paired 't' test, Chi square and Cohen's d were used for statistical analysis. Analyzed data were presented in the form of table, graphs and figures.

Major results

Table: 1 Socio demographic variables of Mothers of Infant in Group I and Group II.

N=500

VARIABLES	GROUP I		GROUP II		p- VALUE
	245	%	234	%	
1. Age in years					
a.21-30	100.0	40.8	101.0	43.2	0.937
b.31-40	143.0	58.4	141.0	60.3	
c. ≥41	7.0	2.9	8.0	3.4	
2. Area of residence					
a. Urban	92.0	37.6	89.0	38.0	0.914
b. Rural	158.0	64.5	161.0	68.8	
3. Type of family					
a. Joint family	59.0	24.1	57.0	24.4	0.612
b. Nuclear family	191.0	78.0	193.0	82.5	
4. Level of education					
a. Diploma / Graduate and above	87.0	35.5	84.0	35.9	0.848
b. High school / higher secondary education	131.0	53.5	133.0	56.8	
c. Primary / secondary education	32.0	13.1	33.0	14.1	
5. Husband's level of education					
a. Diploma / Graduate and above	129.0	52.7	131.0	56.0	0.778
b. High school / higher secondary education	102.0	41.6	99.0	42.3	
c. Primary / secondary education	19.0	7.8	20.0	8.5	

6. Occupation					0.389
a. Government employee	24.0	9.8	29.0	12.4	
b. Private employee	63.0	25.7	52.0	22.2	
c. Daily wages	51.0	20.8	54.0	23.1	
d. Home maker	112.0	45.7	115.0	49.1	
7. Husband's occupation					0.932
a. Government employee	37.0	15.1	40.0	17.1	
b. Private employee	81.0	33.1	83.0	35.5	
c. Self employed	31.0	12.7	32.0	13.7	
d. Daily wages	101.0	41.2	95.0	40.6	
8. Family income per month in Rupees					0.910
a. >40,000	47.0	19.2	43.0	18.4	
b.30, 001 to 40,000	43.0	17.6	40.0	17.1	
c.20, 001 to 30,000	23.0	9.4	25.0	10.7	
d. 10, 001 to 20,000	64.0	26.1	63.0	26.9	
e. ≤ 10,000	73.0	29.8	79.0	33.8	
9. Number of children (Including the present child)					0.722
a. One	162.0	66.1	157.0	67.1	
b. Two	81.0	33.1	84.0	35.9	
c. More than two	7.0	2.9	9.0	3.8	
10. Dietary pattern					0.806
a. Vegetarian	45.0	18.4	43.0	18.4	
b. Ova vegetarian	25.0	10.2	23.0	9.8	
c. Non-vegetarian	98.0	40.0	105.0	44.9	
d. Mixed diet	82.0	33.5	79.0	33.8	
11. Sources of drinking water supply					0.521
a. Open well	12.0	4.9	10.0	4.3	
b. Public tap	141.0	57.6	144.0	61.5	
c. Household tap	97.0	39.6	96.0	41.0	
12. Do you purify the water to drink?					0.834
a. Yes	94.0	38.4	96.0	41.0	
b. No	156.0	63.7	154.0	65.8	
13. Are you aware of Complementary feeding?					0.986

a. Yes	91.0	37.1	89.0	38.0	
b. No	159.0	64.9	161.0	68.8	
If yes, Source of information					0.862
a. Family members / Friends circle	13.0	5.3	15.0	13.0	
b. Printed material / Mass media	30.0	12.2	29.0	30.0	
c. Health workers	39.0	15.9	34.0	39.0	
d. Personal experience	09.0	3.7	11.0	9.0	
14. Who is the primary decision maker on infant feeding?					0.547
a. Myself	17.0	6.9	21.0	9.0	
b. Husband	8.0	3.3	7.0	3.0	
c. Mother in law	38.0	15.5	37.0	15.8	
d. Mother	141.0	57.6	144.0	61.5	
e. Health workers	46.0	18.8	41.0	17.5	
15. Who supports you in infant feeding?					0.775
a. Husband	11.0	4.5	13.0	5.6	
b. Mother in law	24.0	9.8	26.0	11.1	
c. Mother	119.0	48.6	121.0	51.7	
d. Others (specify)...servant....	49.0	20.0	47.0	20.1	
e. No help	47.0	19.2	43.0	18.4	

Table.1 shows that most of the mothers in group I &II in the age group of 31-41 years. Most of the mothers are belongs to urban area in both the groups. Most of the mothers in group I &II were studied up to diploma and graduate level.

Table: 2 Socio demographic Variables of Infant's in Group I and Group II.**N=500**

VARIABLES	GROUP I		GROUP II		p- VALUE
	245	%	234	%	
1. Gender					
a. Male	118.0	48.2	121.0	51.7	0.994
b. Female	132.0	53.9	129.0	55.1	
2. Birth weight					
a. 2 to 2.5 Kg	89.0	36.3	82.0	35.0	0.713
b. 2.51 to 3 Kg	107.0	43.7	108.0	46.2	
c. 3.01 to 3.5 Kg	49.0	20.0	52.0	22.2	
d. >3.51Kg	5.0	2.0	8.0	3.4	
3. Birth order of the infant					
a. First Child	162.0	66.1	157.0	67.1	0.722
b. Second Child	81.0	33.1	84.0	35.9	
c. \geq three Child	7.0	2.9	9.0	3.8	
4. Whether the child was vaccinated?					
a. Yes	224.0	91.4	223.0	95.3	0.318
b. No	26.0	10.6	27.0	11.5	

Table: 2 show that more than 50% of infants were females. Most of the infant's birth weight was between 2.51 to 3.00kgs. Birth order of the majority of the infant's was first order and nearly 90 % of infant's were vaccinated up to their age.

Table: 3 Pre and Post Test Knowledge of Mothers of Infant in Group I and Group II

N=500

GROUP I			GROUP II		
TEST	Mean	SD	TEST	Mean	SD
Pre	15.60	2.66	Pre	15.25	2.62
Post	27.35	1.57	Post	16.45	2.09
MD	11.74	-	MD	1.2	-
SD	2.11	-	SD	2.35	-
Cohen's 'd'	5.566	Effect size 0.7	Cohen's 'd'	0.509	Effect size 0.1

Table: 3 Shows that the pre & post test mean knowledge score of the mothers in group I was 15.60 & 27.35. The mean difference was 11.74 and the average SD was 2.11. The study results shows that the pre & post test mean knowledge score of the mothers in group II was 15.25 & 16.45. The mean difference was 1.2 and the average SD was 2.35.

Figure: 2. Comparison of Knowledge of mothers of infant on complementary feeding in Group I and Group II

COMPARISON OF KNOWLEDGE OF MOTHERS OF INFANT ON COMPLEMENTARY FEEDING IN GROUP I & II

Figure: 2. shows that Comparison of Knowledge of mothers of infant on complementary feeding in Group I and Group II. Knowledge of mothers of infant in group I and group II were assessed after test by questionnaires, before test scores as follows: adequate knowledge n=0 (0%), n=0 (0%), moderately adequate knowledge n=142 (57%), n=136 (54%), inadequate knowledge n=108 (43%), n=114 (46%) and after test scores as follows: adequate knowledge n=221 (93%), n=7 (3%), moderately adequate knowledge n=16 (7%), n=148(63%) inadequate knowledge n=0 (0%), n=79 (34%).

Post test scores of Group I as follows: mean and SD 27.3±1.57, SE-0.83, Cohen's'd' 5.20, Effect size 0.7. Group II score were mean and SD 16.4±2.62, SE-0.52, t value-1.95, Cohen's'd' 0.50, Effect size 0.1.

Table: 4 Anthropometry Status of Infant at 9months and 12 Months in Group I and Group II Before and After Test

N=500

Anthropometry	Group I	Group II	MD	Independent t-Test P Value(0.05)
weight(Kg)				
Baseline	4.74±0.86	4.75±0.89	510g	t=2.58 P=0.001(NS)
6months	6.76±0.88	6.41±0.80		
9months	7.52±0.84	7.05±0.89		
12months	8.24±1.16	7.73±0.87		
length(cm)				
Baseline	60.50±3.42	60.23±3.32	0.65CM	t=0.58 P=0.001(NS)
6months	64.40±3.45	64.32±3.35		
9months	70.50±3.12	70.22±3.03		
12months	75.20±3.02	74.55±3.02		
MAUC(cm)				
6months	12.50±0.96	12.22±1.07	1.0 CM	t=2.58 P=0.001(NS)
	12.30±1.02	12.18±1.08		
9months	12.70±1.04	12.30±1.09		
12months	13.50±1.06	12.50±0.98		

Table: 4 shows the anthropometric status of infant's in group I and group II, its revealed that the infant status were as follows normal nutrition n=194 (79%), n=112 (47%), under nutrition n=35 (14%), n=90(38%), severely under nutrition n=11 (4%), n=22 (9%) and over nutrition 06 (2%), 15 (6%). After test, results shows that infants in the group I had a higher mean weight of 510 g (p=0.001), length of 0.65 cm (p=0.001), and MUAC of 1.0 cm (p=0.001) compared to the group II

Table: 5 Morbidity Status of Infant's at 9 months and 12 Months in Group I and Group II.

N=500

GROUP I											GROUP II									
Months	Presence of illness		No illness		Mild illness		Moderate illness		Severe illness		Presence of illness		No illness		Mild illness		Moderate illness		Severe illness	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
9	27	11	218	89	14	52	11	41	2	7	218	89	128	54	45	35	61	48	22	17
12	10	4	235	96	7	70	3	30	0	0	235	96	137	59	48	35	63	46	26	19

Table: 5. shows the morbidity status of infant was analyzed at 9 months among group I the majority of infant's 218 (89%) had no illness were as 27 (11%) of infant's had illness in which 14 (52%) had exhibited minor illness, 11 (41%) had exhibited moderate illness and 2 (7%) infant's with severe illness. At 9 months among group II infants had no illness 111 (46%) were as majority of infants 128 (54%) had illness in which 45 (35%) had exhibited minor illness, 61 (48%) had exhibited moderate illness and 22 (17%) infant's exhibited severe illness.

At 12 months among group I the majority of infant's 235 (96%) had no illness were as 10 (4.0%) of infant's had illness in which 7 (70%) had exhibited minor illness, 3 (30%) had exhibited moderate illness and 0 (0%) no infant's with severe illness. At 12 months among group II infants had no illness 97 (41%) were as majority of infants 137 (59%) had illness in which 48 (35%) had exhibited minor illness, 63 (46%) had exhibited moderate illness and 26 (19%) infant's exhibited severe illness.

Figure: 3. Correlation between Knowledge of Mothers and Morbidity Status of Infant's in Group I and Group II

N=500

Figure: 3. Shows Correlation between Knowledge of Mothers and Morbidity Status of Infant in Group I and II. Comparison of mothers knowledge on complementary feeding and morbidity status of infants results shows that Group I and II were as follows, $r = -0.427$, $r = -0.139$. It's clearly stating that improvement in mother's knowledge reducing the morbidity status of infants.

Chapter-6

Discussion

Socio demographic Variables of Mothers of Infants and Infants in Group I and Group II.

The study results show that most of the mothers in group I & II in the age group of 31-41 years. Most of the mother's in group I & II residing at urban area. Majority of the mothers in group I & II belongs to nuclear family. Most of the mothers in group I & II were studied up to diploma and graduate level. The results show that most of the mothers in group I & II were belongs to home maker. Most of the mother's husbands working as daily wages.

The study results shows that most of the mother's family income both in group I & II was less than Rs.10000, majority of the mothers in group I & II had one child, most of the mothers in group I & II were belongs to mixed vegetarian diet and most of the mothers in group I & II were getting water from the public tap and majority of them were drinking non purified water. The study findings shows that nearly 60% of the mother's in group I & II were not aware of complementary feeding and around 40% of the mother's who aware of complementary feeding through health workers. The results shows that the important person for decision making in their family were the mother's of the study participants both in group I and II. The study findings also shows that nearly 50% of the mother's in group I & II were received support from their husband's to give complementary feeding.

Socio demographic Variables of Infants in Group I and Group II.

The study results show that more than 50% of infants were females. Most of the infant's birth weight was between 2.51 to 3.00kgs. Birth order of the majority of the infants was first order. The findings show that nearly 90 % of infant's were vaccinated up to their age.

Comparison of mother's knowledge on complementary feeding in group I & II

Knowledge of mother's of infant in group I and group II were assessed before test by questionnaires, scores as follows: adequate knowledge n=0 (0%), n=0 (0%) ,moderately adequate knowledge n=142 (57%), n=136 (54%), inadequate knowledge n=108 (43%), n=114 (46%).

Knowledge of mother's of infant in group I and group II were assessed after test by questionnaires, scores as follows: adequate knowledge n=221 (93%), n=7 (3%), moderately adequate knowledge n=16 (7%), n=148(63%) inadequate knowledge n=0 (0%), n=79 (34%).

Group I mean and SD 27.3±1.57, SE-0.83, Cohen's 'd' 5.20, Effect size 0.7, Group II mean and SD 16.4±2.62, SE-0.52, t value-1.95, Cohen's 'd' 0.50, Effect size 0.1. It showed that group I had adequate knowledge when compare to group II.

Anthropometry Status of Infant's at 9 months and 12 Months in Group I and Group II before and after Test

The study results shows that the anthropometric status of infant's at 9 months in group I and group II were as follows: normal nutrition n=194 (79%), n=112 (47%), under nutrition n=35 (14%), n=90 (38%), severely under nutrition n=11 (4%), n=22 (9%) and over nutrition 06 (2%), 15 (6%). Anthropometric status of infant's also measured at 12 months in group I and group II were as follows: normal nutrition n=221 (90%), n=101 (43%), under nutrition n=13 (5%), n=87(37%), severely under nutrition n=6 (2%), n=29 (12%) and over nutrition 05 (2%), 17 (7%).

After test results shows that infants in the study group I had a higher mean weight of 510 g (p=0.001), length of 0.65 cm (p=0.001), and MUAC of 1.0 cm (p=0.001) compared to the control group II.

Morbidity Status of Infant's at 9 months and 12 Months in Group I and Group II.

The study findings shows that the morbidity status of infant was analyzed at 9 months among group I the majority of infant's 218 (89%) had no illness were as 27 (11%) of infant's had illness in which 14 (52%) had exhibited minor illness, 11 (41%) had exhibited moderate illness and 2 (7%) infant's with severe illness. At 9 months among group II infants had no illness 111 (46%) were as majority of infants 128 (54%) had illness in which 45 (35%) had exhibited minor illness, 61 (48%) had exhibited moderate illness and 22 (17%) infant's exhibited severe illness.

At 12 months among group I the majority of infant's 235 (96%) had no illness were as 10 (4.0%) of infant's had illness in which 7 (70%) had exhibited minor illness, 3 (30%) had exhibited

moderate illness and 0 (0%) no infant's with severe illness. At 12 months among group II infants had no illness 97 (41%) were as majority of infants 137 (59%) had illness in which 48 (35%) had exhibited minor illness, 63 (46%) had exhibited moderate illness and 26 (19%) infant's exhibited severe illness. It showed that group I infant's exhibited lesser illness than the group II infant's.

Correlation between Knowledge of Mother's on complementary feeding and Morbidity Status of Infant's in Group I & II

Comparison of mother's knowledge on complementary feeding and morbidity status of infant's in Group I and II were as follows: $r = -0.427$, $r = -0.139$. It's clearly reveal that improvement in mother's knowledge on complementary feeding reflects in reduction of morbidity status of infant's.

Chapter-7

Summary and conclusion

This study showed that the educational intervention i.e. SCFI is effective at increasing the complementary feeding knowledge among mothers' of infant in the target population. The knowledge improvement in the intervention group was 21.7% higher than the control group ($p < 0.0001$), illustrating the educational intervention effectiveness in increasing knowledge on complementary feeding. Mothers' of infant who pass through the intervention achieved good nutritional status for the infants'. The improvements in mothers' knowledge on complementary feeding correlated with the anthropometric and morbidity outcome, supporting that the intervention is an effective tool to cope up with the knowledge required for effective complementary feeding techniques.

Educational interventions targeting the infants' and mothers' of infant population may allow resources to be better used, improvement in mothers' knowledge on complementary feeding followed by improvement in anthropometric outcome and reduction in morbidity status. It was tremendously improving the health of the infants' and significantly reducing the percentage of hospitalization, costs reduced, and nutritional deficiencies reduced. Especially in low and middle-income countries, targeted implementation might reduce health care expenditures. Pediatric health care professionals may adopt this simple, low-cost, low-intensity waiting room intervention, which can be administered as part of a routine well baby clinic visit serving similar populations.

The results suggest that the structured complementary feeding instruction is useful in educating the mothers' of infant. Wait times to see a Pediatrician is provided perfect time to power point show with explanation. Given to the large number of participants' visiting Pediatric clinics, the large effect size observed in this study could result in improvement of knowledge of mothers' on complementary feeding, followed by meaningful reductions in morbidity and improvement in nutritional status infants'. However, further research is needed to address how the intervention can be extended to provide a long lasting effect.

This study results shows that educational intervention on structured complementary feeding advices is useful to improve the mothers knowledge, self-confidence, hygienic practices. This will help to improve the anthropometry and reduce the morbidity status of infant's. Study results also reveal that by promoting healthy growth and development of infant's we can reduce the stress and discomfort of the family, reduce the hospital visits and hospitalization, reduce the financial burden of family and society. The study concludes that knowledge of mothers of infant on Complementary feeding is a peculiar cardinal factor for the reduction of morbidity and mortality especially during the stage of infancy.

References

1. WHO and UNICEF (2016), Joint child malnutrition estimates - Levels and trends, 2016 edition. Pp.2-3.
2. WHO. Global Health Observatory (2015), data on infant mortality and causes of death, Pp.14-18.
3. UNICEF *global databases*. (2017). Pp.2-3.
4. *District human development report*. (2017.) Kancheepuram district.
5. *UNICEF, WHO, World Bank*. (2019). Joint Child Malnutrition dataset. Pp.01-03.
6. *Knowledge*. <https://www.google.com>.
7. WHO. (2017). *Global Nutrition targets 2025 data on to improve maternal, infant and young child Nutrition*. Pp.01-02.
8. Ekerette.E.U.et.al, (2016). *Complementary feeding practices among mothers and nutritional status of infants in Cross River State Nigeria*. Springer plus, PMC. Vol.5. Pp.01-19.
9. Kassa.T.et.al. (2016), Appropriate complementary feeding practices and associated factors among mothers of children age 6–23 months in Southern Ethiopia. *BMC Pediatrics*. Vol.16. Pp.01-10.
10. Gashaw.A.et.al. (2018) 'Mother's Infant and Young Child Feeding (IYCF) knowledge improved timely initiation of complementary feeding of children aged 6–24 months in the rural population of northwest Ethiopia', *BMC Research note*. Vol.11. Pp.02-07.11.
11. Amos.M.et.al. (2011). *Child care practices and the nutritional status of infants of working mothers in day care centers in Nigeria*. *Annals of Biological Research*. Vol.02. Pp.140-148.
12. Divakar.N.S.et.al. (2012). *Effect of educational intervention on growth pattern and feeding practices in children birth to 24 months of age in Udupi District a community based cluster randomized controlled trial*, Inlibnet. Pp.327.
13. Harendra.D.G.et.al. (2013). An interventional study to monitor weight gain in infants using a home based complementary food recipe and a hand blender. *Ceylon medical journal*. Vol.52. Pp.79-83.
14. Swati.K.et.al. (2014) *Mother's Knowledge Regarding Weaning Process in Infant's*. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*. Vol.3. Pp.1194-1195.

15. Riyad.A.et.al.(2016), Factors associated with the early introduction of complementary feeding. . *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. Vol.13. Pp.01-12.
16. Shams et.al. (2016), Determinants of complementary feeding practices among mothers of 6–24 months failure to thrive children based on behavioral analysis phase of precede model, Tehran. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*. Vol.5. Pp.01-05.
17. Christine.H.et.al. (2018). 'Timing of complementary feeding and associations with maternal and infant characteristics: A Norwegian cross-sectional study, *Plos one*. Vol.13. Pp.02-20.
18. Zohra.S.et.al. (2018), *Impact of education and provision of complementary feeding on growth and morbidity in children less than 2 years of age in developing countries: a systematic review*. *BMC Public Health*. Vol.13. Pp.01-10.
19. Saleem.A.F.et.al. (2017). *Impact of Maternal Education about Complementary Feeding on Their Infants' Nutritional Outcomes in Low- and Middle-income Households: A Community-based Randomized Interventional Study in Karachi, Pakistan*. *Journal of Health Popular Nutrition*. Vol.32. Pp.623-633.
20. Wang D.et.al. (2017). *Association between the Infant and Child Feeding Index (ICFI) and nutritional status of 6- to 35-month-old children in rural western China*. *Plos One*. Vol.12. Pp.01-14.
21. Watson.et.al. (2019). *Impact of maternal literacy skills on Child Weight in Mozambique*. *Public Health Thesis, Georgia state University*. Vol.7. Pp.104-111.
22. Kale.et.al. (2014). *Effectiveness of planned health education program on knowledge related to complementary feeding among mothers*. *Innovations in Pharmaceuticals and Pharmacotherapy*. Vol.2. Pp.395-402.

“Computerized Based Complementary Feeding Instructions on Infants Morbidity Status”

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ABSTRACT

Complementary feeding (CF) to infants is an advancement of steadily familiarizing semi-liquid to semi-solid foods along with mom's milk at the end of 6 months. The objectives were to assess the demographic variables of infants, to assess the infant's morbidity status. Methodology: Quantitative approach were used to evaluate the experimental and control groups. The design used in this study was Pretest posttest control group. Sample of 500 mothers and mothers of infant included who satisfying the inclusion criteria chosen by simple Random sampling. Obtained written consent from each participant before collecting the data and confidentiality of data were maintained. The collected data were analyzed by descriptive, inferential statistics. Results: Experimental Group mean SD 27.3±1.57, SE-0.83, Control Group mean SD 16.4±2.62, SE-0.52, Effect size 0.7, t value-1.95, Cohen's „d“ 5.20. At the end of 12 months among experimental group infants had no illness 97 (41%) were as in control group majority of infants 137 (59%) had illness in which 48 (35%) had exhibited minor illness, 63 (46%) had exhibited moderate illness and 26 (19%) infant's exhibited severe illness. It showed that experimental group infant's exhibited lesser illness compared to control group infants.

Key Words: Computerized Instructions, Complementary feeding, Morbidity status, Infants.

INTRODUCTION

Globally 2.8 million children deaths (28% being under five deaths) attributable to child hood under nutrition. India al one has 0.6 million child deaths, and 24.6 million attributed to stunting. Recent scientific evidence reveals that malnutrition has been directly or indirectly involves 60% of under-five year's children die annually¹. World Health Organization reports that mal-nourished children are the important aspect and suffers largely from infection and die from common childhood sicknesses than nourished young children².

According to recent studies, every 3rd deaths in young children aged 5 years or younger is due to under nutrition. Across the board infant nutrition deficiency greatly interfere the India's socio-economic development and chance to scale back economic condition³. World Health Organization (WHO) additionally recommends exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of an infants' life, followed by complementary foods. Breastfeeding to be continued up to a minimum of a two years of recent to guard the infant from varieties of deficiency disease⁴. Likewise, early initiation of breastfeeding is incredibly crucial for survival, growth and nutrition of the newborn. In extension, it's additionally renowned permanently, infants' brain development⁵.

However, in low and middle-income countries like Asian country, perception and acceptance of contemporary birth control ways via breastfeeding are terribly low, this ensuring the deficiency disease to infants'. As per the recent statistics, rates of deficiency disease among India's young children are nearly five times over in China and double those in geographic region^{6,7}. Only „one fourth“ of mothers' of infant begin to initiate the breast feeding within the one hour of delivery and fewer than „half“ all mothers' of infant are able to give exclusive breast feeding for the primary six months after the child birth^{8,9}. Infants' from 6 months to 24 months may be a vulnerable period of childhood. It's the stage to have deficiency disease in several infants', presenting doubtless to the high prevalence of deficiency disease world-wide¹⁰.

Objectives:

1. To assess the pretest and posttest levels of morbidity status of infant on complementary feeding.

2. To compare between control and study groups level of knowledge with selected demographic variables of infant.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research approach:

Quantitative, Evaluative approach give the impression to be the utmost suitable approach for this research study.

Research design:

Pretest-posttest control group research design was appears to be appropriate for this study.

Research setting:

The research study was conducted at Selected Hospital in India.

Sample and sample size:

Infants between age group of 3-12 months and who satisfy the inclusion criteria were included for this study. Based on power analysis Formula $N = p(1-p)(Z/E)^2$, sample size of 500, out of which 250 infants randomly assigned to study group and 250 were assigned to control group. Simple Random sampling technique was used to select the infants.

Sample criteria:

Inclusion criteria;

The study includes infants, who were,

- ❖ aged 3 - 5 months; who are either exclusively breast feed or partially breast feed but have not started complementary feeding.
- ❖ term /appropriate to gestational age.
- ❖ age group between 3months to 1year.
- ❖ attending pediatric outpatient department

The study excludes **Exclusion criteria**

infants, who were, Critically ill.

- ❖ having mal absorption syndrome.
- ❖ Known genetic anomaly, neurological disorder.

SCORE INTERPRETATION

Table (1): Standardized structured questionnaire to assess the morbidity status of infant

S.NO	SCORE	PERCENTAGE	LEVEL OF ILLNESS
1	1-25	≤50	Mild Illness
2	26-37	50-75	Moderate Illness
3	38-50	≥76	Severe Illness

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Structured questionnaire was used to assess the data of demographic variables and the level of morbidity status of infants on complementary feeding. Data was collected after written consent from each participant mother, and confidentiality were maintained.

Research Tool:

Part-I

Selected demographic variables of infants such as age of the child, sex of the child, number of the children, order of children.

Part-II

A structured questionnaire is used to assess the morbidity status of infant at 9 and 12 months, present study focus on Food allergy, loose motion, Dysentery, Respiratory infection, Fever, Worm infestation, any other health problems. It is based on 5 point likert scale and interpretation options as rarely "1" (one), occasionally "2" (two), frequently "3" (three), Often "4" (four), Always "5" (five). The maximum score is 50 and minimum score is 10.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The study results shows that morbidity status of infant's in group I and group II at 9 months were: 131 (53%), 41 (18%) infant's had no illness were as 114 (45%), 193 (82%) infant's had illness in which 65 (27%), 110 (47%) belongs to minor illness, 43 (18%), 61 (26%) had exhibited moderate illness and 6 (2%), 22 (9%) infant's with severe illness respectively. Morbidity status of infant's in group I and group II at 12 months were: 224 (91%) 16 (7%) infant's had no illness were as 21 (9.0%), 218 (93%) infant's had illness in which 15 (6%), 86 (37%) had exhibited minor illness, 6 (3%), 89 (38%) had exhibited moderate illness and 0 (0%), 43 (18%) infant's with severe illness. Group I infants had a lesser morbidity score than the Group II infants respectively, figure I and 2 exhibiting the same.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that Morbidity status of infant's in group I and group II at 12 months were: 224 (91%) 16 (7%) infant's had no illness were as 21 (9.0%), 218 (93%) infant's had illness in which 15 (6%), 86 (37%) had exhibited minor illness, 6 (4%), 89 (38%) had exhibited moderate illness and 0 (0%), 43 (18%) infant's with severe illness. Group I infants had a lesser morbidity score than the Group II infants. The infant's with proper Complementary feeding is a peculiar cardinal factor for the reduction of morbidity and mortality especially during the infancy period.

Conflict of interest- Nil

Source of Funding- Self funding and no external funding.

Ethical Clearance: Obtained clearance from institutional human ethical committee, CARE.

REFERENCES

- [1]. WHO and UNICEF, Joint child malnutrition estimates-Levels and trends, 2016, Pp.2-3.
- [2]. Zaman, S.; Ashraf, R.N.; Martines, J. Training in Complementary Feeding Counselling of Healthcare Workers and Its Influence on Maternal Behaviours and Child Growth: A Cluster-randomized Controlled Trial in Lahore, Pakistan. *J. Heal. Popul. Nutr.* 2008, 26, 210–222.
- [3]. Wang D. et al., *Association between the Infant and Child Feeding Index (ICFI) and nutritional status of 6- to 35-month-old children in rural western China.* *PlosOne.* 2017, Vol. 12. Pp. 01-14.
- [4]. Tylleskar, T.; Jackson, D.; Meda, N.; Engebretsen, I.M.S.; Chopra, M.; Diallo, A.H.; Doherty, T.; Ekström, E.-C.; Fadnes, L.T.; Goga, A.; et al. Exclusive breastfeeding promotion by peer counsellors in sub-Saharan Africa (PROMISE-EBF): A cluster-randomised trial. *Lancet* 2011, 378, 420–427.
- [5]. Younes, L.; Houweling, T.A.; Azad, K.; Kuddus, A.; Shaha, S.; Haq, B.; Nahar, T.; Hossen, M.; Beard, J.; Copas, A.; et al. The effect of participatory women's groups on infant feeding and child health knowledge, behavior and outcomes in rural Bangladesh: A controlled before-and-after study. *J. Epidemiol. Community Health* 2015, 69, 374–381.
- [6]. De Onis, Mercedes et al. (2018) Prevalence thresholds for wasting, overweight and stunting in children under 5 years. *Public Health Nutrition* 22(1):1-5 · October 2018.
- [7]. UNICEF, Improving Child Nutrition: The achievable imperative for global progress, UNICEF, New York, 2013.
- [8]. UNICEF, Progress for Children Beyond Averages: Learning from the MDGs, New York, 2015
- [9]. Black, R.E., et al., income and Middle-income Countries, *Lancet*, vol. 382, no. 9890, 3 August 2013, pp. 427–451.
- [10]. UNICEF/WHO/ World Bank Joint Child Malnutrition Estimates, March 2020 edition.

Knowledge of Mothers of Infant and effects on Morbidity Status of Infants: Computerized structured Complementary Feeding Instructions

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ABSTRACT

Complementary feeding (CF) to infants is an advancement of steadily familiarizing semi-liquid to semi-solid foods along with mom's milk at the end of 6 months. The objectives were to assess the demographic variables of infants and mothers of infant, to assess the infant's morbidity status. Methodology: Quantitative approach were used to evaluate the experimental and control groups. The design used in this study was Pretest posttest control group. Sample of 500 mothers and mothers of infant included who satisfying the inclusion criteria chosen by simple Random sampling. Obtained written consent from each participant before collecting the data and confidentiality of data were maintained. The collected data were analyzed by descriptive, inferential statistics. Results: Experimental Group mean SD 27.3±1.57, SE-0.83, Control Group mean SD 16.4±2.62, SE-0.52, Effect size 0.7, t value-1.95, Cohen's 'd' 5.20,. At the end of 12 months among experimental group infants had no illness 97 (41%) were as in control group majority of infants 137 (59%) had illness in which 48 (35%) had exhibited minor illness, 63 (46%) had exhibited moderate illness and 26 (19%) infant's exhibited severe illness. It showed that experimental group infant's exhibited lesser illness compared to control group infants. Conclusion: A further counseling session, health education on complementary feeding were arranged for both the groups of participant mothers who belongs to moderate and inadequate knowledge score in posttest.

Keywords: Computerized Instructions, Structured Complementary feeding, Knowledge, Morbidity status of infant, Mothers of infant.

INTRODUCTION

Complementary feeding is a process of gradually introducing semi-liquid to semi-solid foods along with breast milk at the completion of 6 months till 2 years [1].

“Complementary feeding to infants” is the process of starting when breast milk alone is no longer sufficient to meet the nutritional requirements of an infant's. It should be initiated at the completion of 6 months and it should be age-appropriate feeding as follows, semi liquid, liquid, liquid, semi-solid, solid and soft foods along with breastfeeding [2].

The transition of food pattern will enhance the children growth, which triples the birth weight by the end of the one year [3].

Morbidity is defined as unhealthy physical and mental state of the infant. The first two years of childhood period is very crucial and more prone to infection and illnesses. Common childhood illnesses like fever, respiratory illness, vomiting, diarrhea, dysentery, constipation, worm infestations are having very poor prognosis when the child is with Malnutrition [4].

Every 6 seconds 1 infant is dying by malnutrition. The infant mortality rate of the world-according to the United

Nations 42.09 and as per World bank is 49.4. In 2015, 4.5 million (75%) of all under-five deaths occurred within the first year of life [6].

World Health Organization reports that mal-nourished children are the important aspect and suffers largely from infection and die from common childhood sicknesses than nourished young children [7].

The UN estimates that 2.1 million Indian children die before reaching the age of 5 year. Four children die every minute due to preventable illnesses such as diarrhea, typhoid, malaria, measles and pneumonia. Every day 1,000 Indian children die because of diarrhea alone. According to UNICEF worldwide statistics (2018), only two fifths of infants of 0-6 months age are breastfed exclusively. Only around two thirds are introduced to solid foods in a timely manner. Global Infant mortality rate is 13 deaths / 1000 live births [13], [14].

This study is an educational intervention trial on complementary feeding to enhance the mothers' knowledge, which influence the infants' morbidity outcome in a chosen settings.

Research Questions

1. Developed knowledge assessment tool on complementary feeding is valid and reliable for the target population?
2. Developed Structured complementary feeding instructions will prove as an effective interventional instrument?
3. Does educational intervention on Complementary feeding may decline the morbidity rate of an infant and improve the level of mothers' knowledge?

Objectives

1. To assess the pre and posttest knowledge on complementary feeding among mothers of infants.
2. To assess the pretest and posttest levels of morbidity status of infant on complementary feeding.
3. To find out the correlation between the knowledge of mothers of infant with morbidity status of infant.

Operational Definition

1. Structured Complementary Feeding:

It refers to the instruction systematically planned and organized feeding such as exclusive breast feeding, maintenance of breast feeding, introduction of complementary feeding, responsive feeding, safe preparation and storage, amount of food consistency, meal frequency and energy requirements, food consistency, nutrients and use of vitamin-mineral supplements for infant, feeding during and after illness, maternal health-food pattern of mother during feeding which will be given as instruction with the help of computer to the mothers of infant.

2. Level of Knowledge:

It refers to the relevant information of mothers of infant regarding complementary feeding which will be evaluated through structured questionnaire, Correct responses of mothers are further classified into adequate ($\geq 76\%$) moderate (51-75%) and inadequate ($\leq 50\%$), experts certified.

3. Mothers' of infant:

Mothers who were eligible and willing to participate and who understands Tamil in the age group of 21-50 years & having infant 3-12 months attending well baby clinic for infant immunization and plan to have all immunization at a Selected Tertiary Care Hospital.

4. Morbidity status:

Morbidity refers to describe how often a disease occurs among infants Which includes,

1. Food allergy
2. Loose motion
3. Bloody loose motion
4. Respiratory infection
5. Fever
6. Worm infestation
7. Any other health problems

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

"A study by Swati Kambli, have conducted a study on Mothers knowledge on weaning process in infants, 50 mothers of infants aged 6 to 12 months, pediatric department by using Quasi experimental explorative research with Purposive sampling technique, the study results shows that 42% mothers poor knowledge, 38% average knowledge

and 20% good knowledge. The author has concluded that update the mothers about the existing or current recommendations through education to reduce the mortality and morbidity of infants” [12].

“A study by sasikavitha., have conducted a study on Study of Complementary feeding practices, 50 mothers of infants aged 6 to 12 months, hospital setting, Salem by using Cross sectional study with simple random sampling technique, The study results shows that 62% mothers introduced complementary foods before 5 months, while 36 % introduced at 6 months, The author has concluded that Education & counseling of mothers about complementary feeding will enhance a timely complementary feeding” [11].

“A study by Riyad A, have conducted a study on Factors associated with the early introduction of complementary feeding, 632 mothers of infants 3- 12 months attending PHC In Saudi Arabia. The study results shows that 62.7% of study infants received early initiation of complementary feeding before 17 weeks by using Questionnaire method simple random method, The author have concluded that Public health educational interventions are needed to reduce early complementary feeding” [9].

A study was conducted on Infant at the Age of 6 Months in relation to Feeding Practices, Iron Status, and Growth in a Peri-Urban Community of South Africa concluded that Prevalence of anemia and stunting for the infants were 36.4% and 28.5%, respectively. Multiple regression analysis showed that birth weight was related to combined psychomotor scores as well as parent rating scores „Length-for-age z-scores were associated with combined psychomotor scores ($\beta = -1.419 (-2.466, 0.373)$, $p = 0.008$), as well as parent rating scores ($\beta = -0.747 (-1.483, -0.010)$, $p = 0.047$)” [10].

METHODS

Research approach

Quantitative, Evaluative approach was chosen for this study.

Research design

Pretest-posttest control group design was suitable for this study.

Research setting

This research study was well planned and conducted at Selected Hospital in Tamilnadu, India.

Sample and sample size

Infants and mothers of infants the age group from 3 to 12 months and who consistently satisfy the selected inclusion criteria were recruited for this study. Power analysis Formula $N = \frac{p(1-p)(Z/E)^2}{}$, sample size of 500 infants and mothers of infants, out of which 250 in to study group and 250 in to control group. Simple random sampling technique was used to recruited the Participants.

Sample criteria for infants and mothers:

Inclusion criteria;

The study recruits the infants, who were,

- ✓ aged from 3 - 5 months,
- ✓ one or the other exclusively breast feeding or incompletely breast feeding however not started complementary feeding,
- ✓ term /appropriate to gestational age,
- ✓ age from 3months to 1year,
- ✓ Presenting in the pediatric outpatient department.

The study includes mothers of infants who were,

- ✓ Can read, write and understand Tamil or English.

Exclusion criteria;

The study excludes infants, who were,

- ✓ critically ill,
- ✓ having mal absorption syndrome,
- ✓ known genetic anomaly,
- ✓ neurological disorder.

The study excludes mothers of infant who were,

- ✓ having adequate knowledge pretest score ($\geq 76\%$),

fails to give consent for any reason, sick.

Data Collection Procedure

Pre tested structured questionnaire was used to assess the variables and the level of mother's knowledge and morbidity status of infants on complementary feeding on scheduled timings. Data was collected after written consent from each participant. Anonymity, freedom to withdraw from the study at any time during the study and confidentiality were maintained [8].

RESULTS

Mothers of infant in the group I had a higher Knowledge score, mean and SD 27.3 ± 1.57 , SE-0.83, Cohen's "d" 5.20, Effect size 0.7 compared to group II score, mean and SD 16.4 ± 2.62 , SE-0.52, t value-1.95, Cohen's "d" 0.50, Effect size 0.1.

Morbidity status of infant's in group I and group II at 9 months were: 131 (53%), 41 (18%) infant's had no illness were as 114 (45%), 193 (82%) infant's had illness in which 65 (27%), 110 (47%) belongs to minor illness, 43 (18%), 61 (26%) had exhibited moderate illness and 6 (2%), 22 (9%) infant's with severe illness respectively. Morbidity status of infant's in group I and group II at 12 months were: 224 (91%) 16 (7%) infant's had no illness were as 21 (9.0%), 218 (93%) infant's had illness in which 15 (6%), 86 (37%) had exhibited minor illness, 6 (3%), 89 (38%) had exhibited moderate illness and 0 (0%), 43 (18%) infant's with severe illness. Group I infants had a lesser morbidity score than the Group II infants respectively.

The study findings shows that the morbidity status of infant was analyzed at 9 months among group I the majority of infant's 131 (53%) had no illness (Fig.1) were as 114 (47%) of infant's had illness (Fig. 6.7) in which 65 (27%) had exhibited minor illness, 43 (18%) had exhibited moderate illness and 6 (2%) infant's with severe illness.

Fig: 1-.Change in illness of infants at different time points

Fig: 2- Changes in no illness at different time points

Fig: 3- Status of infant morbidity at 9 months

Morbidity status of infant's in group I and group II at 9 months were: 131 (53%), 41 (18%) infant's had no illness were as 114 (45%), 193 (82%) infant's had illness in which 65 (27%), 110 (47%) belongs to minor illness, 43 (18%), 61 (26%) had exhibited moderate illness and 6 (2%), 22 (9%) infant's with severe illness, It is clearly denoted in figure(3).

Morbidity Status of Infant's at 12 Months

Morbidity status of infant's in group I and group II at 12 months were: 224 (91%) 16 (7%) infant's had no illness were as 21 (9.0%), 218 (93%) infant's had illness in which 15 (6%), 86 (37%) had exhibited minor illness, 6 (4%), 89 (38%) had exhibited moderate illness and 0 (0%), 43 (18%) infant's with severe illness. Group I infants had a lesser morbidity score than the Group II infants, It is represented in figure (4).

Fig: 4- Status of infant morbidity at 12 months

The decrease in morbidity from the both the groups followed a linear model (Fig. 1-4). The curve fit analysis shows 10.3 fold illness reduction by efficacy of educational intervention is achieved in group I.

Fig: 5- Correlation between Knowledge of Mothers and Morbidity Status of Infant's in Group 1

Fig: 6-Correlation between Knowledge of Mothers and Morbidity Status of Infant’s in Group II

Figure 5 and 6 Shows Correlation between Knowledge of Mothers and Morbidity Status of Infant in Group I and II. Comparison the scores of mothers knowledge on complementary feeding and morbidity status of infants in Group I and II respectively, $r = -0.427$, $r = -0.139$. It’s clearly stating that improvement in Group I compared to Group II.

SUMMARY

This study showed that the educational intervention i.e. SCFI is effective at increasing the complementary feeding knowledge among mothers” of infant in the target population. The knowledge improvement in the intervention group was 21.7% higher than the control group ($p < 0.0001$), illustrating the educational intervention effectiveness in increasing knowledge on complementary feeding. Mothers” of infant who pass through the intervention achieved good nutritional status for the infants”. The improvements in mothers” knowledge on complementary feeding correlated with the anthropometric and morbidity outcome, supporting that the intervention is an effective tool to cope up with the knowledge required for effective complementary feeding techniques.

CONCLUSION

This study results shows that educational intervention on structured complementary feeding instructions is essential to improve the mothers knowledge, self-confidence and hygienic practices. Mothers” knowledge definitely influencing by reducing the morbidity status of infant”s. The study concludes that knowledge of mothers” of infant on Complementary feeding is a peculiar cardinal factor for the growth, reduction of morbidity and mortality especially during the stage of infancy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- ✓ A study can be conducted to assess the role of the care givers in the complementary feeding.
- ✓ A study can be conducted in different settings such as the rural and urban area to identify the complementary feeding practices
- ✓ A study can be conducted to compare between both genders.
- ✓ A longitudinal study can be carried out
- ✓ A qualitative time series study may be carried out.

REFERENCES

- [1] Agrasada, G.V.; Ewald, U.; Kylberg, E.; Gustafsson, J. Exclusive breastfeeding of low birth weight infants for the first six months: Infant morbidity and maternal and infant anthropometry. *Asia Pac. J. Clin. Nutr.* 2011.
- [2] Aidam, B. A., Pérez-Escamilla, R., Lartey, A., & Aidam, J. (2005). Factors associated with exclusive breastfeeding in Accra, Ghana. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 59(6), 789–796. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602144>

- [3] Bhandari, N., Bahl, R., Mazumdar, S., Martines, J., Black, R. E., & Bhan, M. K. (2003). Effect of community-based promotion of exclusive breastfeeding on diarrhoeal illness and growth: a cluster randomised controlled trial. *The Lancet*, 361(9367), 1418–1423. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(03\)13134-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(03)13134-0)
- [4] Christian, P.; Shaikh, S.; Shamim, A.A.; Mehra, S.; Wu, L.; Mitra, M.; Ali, H.; Merrill, R.D.; Choudhury, N.; Parveen, M.; et al. Effect of fortified complementary food supplementation on child growth in rural Bangladesh: A cluster-randomized trial. *Int. J. Epidemiology* 2015, 44, 1862–1876
- [5] De Oliveira, L.D.; Giugliani, E.; Santo, L.C.D.E.; França, M.C.T.; Weigert, E.M.L.; Kohler, C.V.F.; Bonilha, A.L.D.L. Effect of Intervention to Improve Breastfeeding Technique on the Frequency of Exclusive Breastfeeding and Lactation-Related Problems. *J. Hum. Lact.* 2016, 22, 315–321.
- [6] Flax, V.L.; Negerie, M.; Ibrahim, A.U.; Leatherman, S.; Daza, E.J.; Bentley, M.E. Integrating Group Counseling, Cell Phone Messaging, and Participant-Generated Songs and Dramas into a Microcredit Program Increases Nigerian Women's Adherence to International Breastfeeding Recommendations–3. *J. Nutr.* 2014, 144, 1120–1124.
- [7] Grellety, E., Shepherd, S., Roederer, T., Manzo, M. L., Doyon, S., Ategbo, E.-A., & Grais, R. F. (2012). Effect of Mass Supplementation with Ready-to-Use Supplementary Food during an Anticipated Nutritional Emergency. *PLoS ONE*, 7(9), e44549. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0044549>.
- [8] Palanimuthu, K. (2018). Knowledge assessment tool on complementary feeding among mothers of infants: reliability and validity. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 51(3), 93–95. http://ijrar.com/upload_issue/ijrar.
- [9] Riyad.A.et.al., Factors associated with the early introduction of complementary feeding. . *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2016, Vol.13. Pp.01-12.
- [10] Rothman M, Faber M, Covic N, Matsungu TM, Cockeran M, Kvalsvig JD, Smuts CM.et. al. (2018), Infant at the Age of 6 Months in relation to Feeding Practices, Iron Status, and Growth in a Peri-Urban Community of South Africa. *Cochrane Database Systematic Review*. 2017, 11.
- [11] Saikavitha, C.Nadhiya, Dr.R.Parimalavalli, 'Study of Complementary feeding practices among mothers of infants aged six months to one year. ', *Healthline*, 2018, 5(2), pp. 29-
- [12] Swati.K.et.al. *Mother's Knowledge Regarding Weaning Process in Infant's*. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*. 2014, Vol.3. Pp.1194-1195.
- [13] Zachariassen, G., Faerk, J., Grytter, C., Esberg, B., Juvonen, P., & Halken, S. (2010). Factors associated with successful establishment of breastfeeding in very preterm infants. *Acta Paediatrica*, 99(7), 1000–1004. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1651-2227.2010.01721.x>
- [14] Zaman, S.; Ashraf, R.N.; Martines, J. Training in Complementary Feeding Counselling of Healthcare Workers and Its Influence on Maternal Behaviours and Child Growth: A Cluster-randomized Controlled Trial in Lahore, Pakistan. *J. Heal. Popul. Nutr.* 2008, 26, 210–222.